

TEACHING OF PHRASEOLOGICAL COMBINATIONS IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATION

Karimova Munisaxon Hayotjon qizi

A student of Kokand state pedagogical institute,
department of Pre-school education

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8019543>

Annotation: Today, the cultural study of the development of phraseological units in the language in linguistics shows the relationship between language and culture, because stable phrases are more related to the life of the people than other linguistic units of the language.

Keywords: phraseology, phrase, phraseological combination, linguistic feature, cultural feature, linguoculturology.

Various features of phraseological expressions can be determined by classification according to external form. In this classification, more attention is paid to the number of words in phraseological expressions. As a result of the classification, it is possible to determine how many words are made up of phrases according to their nature. Many linguists are of the opinion that phraseological expressions are only more than two words. But observations show that phraseological expressions consist of two, three or more words. But some linguists think that there are also one-word phrases. In particular, according to Professor Jafarov, phrases consisting of one word are formed at the highest stage of development of idiomatic expressions. Expressions of this type are expressed by a compound word or a single word, they differ from compound words in that they cannot express a direct thought. An idiomatic meaning can also be understood through a single word. But it is difficult to call such words a phrase. Because a phrase must consist of a combination of words.

Phraseological combinations mainly consist of a combination of words, in other words, phraseologisms are a separate unit of the language, which according to their structure are freely connected or equal to a sentence, fully or partially semantically reshaped figurative, stable word combinations. includes. Most of the phraseologisms, both in English and in other languages, were created by the people, their authors are not known, and the sources of origin are not clear. In this sense, the phraseological scientist Kunin, the author of most of the phraseologisms of the English language, is unknown, and he justified the opinion that they were created by the people. But it is possible to determine the sources of origin of some phraseological units. In this sense, phraseology is a microsystem that is part of the general system of language, and this system reflects past heritage, values, and is passed from generation to generation. Most

of the phraseological units that make up the system are a rich source of a given language.

The relationship between phraseological units and their main components makes up the phraseological system. Phraseologisms are combinations of words composed of more than one word, stable in meaning and form. Phraseologisms are used figuratively, in figurative expressions, and have historical norms and methods of use, and their meaning is clarified in the course of a certain speech. Phraseologisms are in the form of phrases or sentences, they differ from sentences that are speech units. As a lexical unit, they are close to words in many respects, a lot of features characteristic of words are also characteristic of phraseologisms. There are different assumptions when defining the object of phraseology. The object of phraseology consists only of stable compounds. The science of phraseology is defined as a science that studies the structural properties of phraseological units, their appearance in the language system and the features of their use. Words and phrases from the holy religious book are widely presented in the book "Studies in English, Written and Spoken" by S.Stoffen. In the chapter "Scriptural phrases and Allusions in Modern", the scientist studies and scientifically analyzes biblical phrases and their etymology. In Western linguistics, the study of biblicisms is again associated with the name of L.P. Smith. In his book "Phraseology of the English Language", he devoted a separate section to biblical phrases and studied them. The author writes that "the number of biblical idioms and expressions in the English language is so great that it is not an easy task to collect and list them." L.P. Smith notes that the English language contains not only many biblical words, but also biblical idiomatic expressions that represent the literal translation of ancient Hebrew and Greek idioms.

Biblical Phraseological Phrases Phraseological phrases in English with a food component include food names such as "apple", "bread", "milk", "fat", "olive". There are also phraseological units related to place names in English. Their analysis and research can be found in the scientific work of M. Rajabova. The study of place names is considered not only as an object of linguistics, but also of history and geography. Linguistic and cultural research of the phraseologisms with place names, highlighting their national and cultural aspects is one of the urgent issues of modern linguistics. The following units can be cited as examples of phraseologisms related to place names: have kissed the Blarney stone In Ireland, there is a big stone in front of Blarney Castle, and according to the legends of the English people, a person who kisses this stone

will have the vice of flattery and flattery; go for a Burton - to die, close your eyes, disappear without a trace. Barton is a small brewing town in Staffordshire. This phrase was first used by British pilots during World War II to remember their comrades-in-arms who died in the war. L.P. Smith notes that the English language contains not only a number of biblical words, but also biblical idiomatic expressions that show a literal translation of ancient Hebrew and Greek idioms. For example, Adam's apple - a phraseological unit with a food component - is translated as "stew", "lark apple".

Phraseological conflicts are phraseologisms whose component meanings are unrelated to the meaning of the whole unit. For example, heavy father - the main role in a theater play, to kick the bucket - to die, red tape - bureaucratic methods are phraseologisms that give one meaning as a whole, the meaning of which does not depend on the meaning of the words in their composition. Phraseological phrases are combinations of words whose meaning has completely changed. But unlike phraseological compounds, the meaning of which cannot be understood from the meaning of its constituent parts, the transfer of meaning based on metaphor loses its clarity. Phraseologisms such as To leave smb in lunch (to abandon a friend when he is in trouble), to show the white feather (to betray one's cowardice), to dance attendance on smb (to try and attract smb, to show exaggerated attention) also belong to phraseological conflicts can be an example. Phraseological compounds are phraseological units whose meaning is understood from the phraseological meaning of a whole set of phraseological units. The transfer of meaning based on metaphor is clear and obvious. Lexical components of phraseological compounds are the most stable. Phraseological associations are made up of words that have a specific valence. One of the components of such phraseological units is used in its proper sense, and the rest in a metaphorical sense. Phraseological associations are to some extent semantically indivisible. Phraseological associations are combinations of words whose meaning has partially changed. The meaning of these phraseological units is easily understood from the meaning of the words that make them up. In conclusion, the semantic aspects of the phraseological units related to the profession show that they are related to the physical labor of a person in both languages, they express the concepts directly related to the labor activity of a person.

References:

1. Sapayeva Z. Semantic and linguocultural analysis of phraseology in English and Uzbek languages. Tashkent. 2023.
2. Mamatov A.E. Formation of Uzbek phraseology. Tashkent. 1997

3. Narimonova Z. About the translation of phraseological expressions. Tashkent. 2007.
4. Niyazmetova D. Phraseologisms with food component in English linguistic research. Scientific Information. 2012
5. Karimova, V. V., & Karimova, M. (2022). SUPPLETIVISM OF THE LEXICAL PLAN IN THE TURKIC LANGUAGES (BASED ON THE TERMS OF KINSHIP IN THE UZBEK LANGUAGE). *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(11), 1245-1249.
6. Karimova, V. V., & Karimova, M. (2022). REASONING ON THE HISTORY OF THE STUDY OF KINSHIP TERMS IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(11), 1227-1233.
7. Karimova, V. V., & Karimova, M. (2023). Some Facts About The Comparative Study Of Kinship Terms (In English And Uzbek Language Materials). *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, 921-927.
8. Karimova, V. A. BRIEF OVERVIEW OF THE HISTORY OF THE STUDY OF THE TERMS OF KINSHIP IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH.
9. Расулова, Ш. Х., & Каримова, В. В. (2020). Об ономасиологическом аспекте изучения терминов родства женского пола в узбекском и таджикском языках. *Вестник Бохтарского государственного университета имени Носира Хусрава. Серия гуманитарных и экономических наук*, (1-1), 75-78.
10. Rajarova, M. (2022). Allegorical Means Specific to Oral Speech. *Scienceweb academic papers collection*.
11. Sotvoldiyev, I., & Rajarova, M. (2023). EASY METHODS OF READING AND READING STRATEGIES. *International Conference On Higher Education Teaching*, 1(3), 133-139. Retrieved from <https://aidlix.com/index.php/de/article/view/70>
12. Ҳайдарова, Г. А. (2022). XX АСР ЎЗБЕК ҒАЗАЛЛАРИНИНГ ВАЗН ХУСУСИЯТИГА ДОИР. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2(6), 241-245.
13. Ismatova, N. M. (2021). PRINCIPLES OF TOPONYMS CLASSIFICATIONS. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(3), 1025-1029.
14. Makhmudovna, I. N. (2022). Some Types of Toponyms. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION*, 2(2), 478-480.
15. Makhmudovna, I. N. (2022). Generallegislation of toponymics and the concept of toponymy. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 12(5), 704-706.

16. Makhmudovna, I. N. (2022). TOPONYMS CONSTRUCTED BY COMPOUND NOUNS WITH THE COLOR COMPONENT. Berlin Studies Transnational Journal of Science and Humanities, 2(1.6 Philological sciences).
17. Aliyevna, Y. D. (2023). Study Of Concepts Expressing The Relationship Between New And Old Information (Theme And Rheme) Expressed In A Sentence. Journal of Positive School Psychology, 551-554.
18. Yuldasheva, D. A. (2017). Innovative methods of teaching English to young children. Molodoy uchenyy, (4.2), 138-2.
19. Karimova, V. V., & Yuldasheva, D. A. (2016). The Responsibility of a Teacher for Increasing the Probability of Advancing Student Achievement. Molodoy uchenyy, 3-1.
20. Yuldasheva, D. (2023). SUB'YEKTNING BADIY DISKURSDAGI FUNKSIYASI. Педагогика и психология в современном мире: теоретические и практические исследования, 2(8), 95-98.

